

Deliverable Report D7.1

Project Internal Ethical Guideline

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FFP	Fabrication, Falsification, or Plagiarism
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PC	Project Coordinator
R&I	Research & Innovation
SSbD	Safe & Sustainable by Design
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The INSIGHT Project activities are guided by several European regulations and guidelines including:

- Horizon Europe regulation 2021/695 (Articles 18 and 19),
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity,
- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of The European Union (2000/C 364/01)
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), and
- The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship.

The Ethical Guideline document is a living document, which will be updated regularly and will support the beneficiaries in ethical compliance. The report is based on the INSIGHT Grant Agreement (GA), mainly on Articles 14 and 15, and Annex 5. Additional agreements between beneficiaries are described in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All beneficiaries are expected to follow strictly the provisions of both the GA and CA, throughout the Project duration. This document seeks to further clarify and guide the underlying measures expected to be ensured, and the corresponding activities conducted within the Project. The document touches on ethical topics that should be respected in research concerning e.g. research integrity and transparency of research results and specifically data storage, personal data protection and artificial intelligence. The ethical guidelines will be implemented by the WP leaders and regularly updated and adapted, if necessary, by the Executive Board of the Project.

I Aim and Goal of the INSIGHT Ethical Guideline

The INSIGHT Ethical Guideline outlines the underlying activities that the consortium must consider at all steps of their research and innovation (R&I) activities, and describe processes for reviews of privacy-, ethics- and gender issues as and when these become necessary; these activities and processes will be elaborated by the INSIGHT Executive Board (Project Coordinator and WP Leaders).

I.1 INSIGHT Proposal Stipulations regarding Ethics & Security

The consortium that drafted the INSIGHT Project proposal has performed an initial assessment of INSIGHT ethics during the proposal submission phase and provided information about the Project's planned concerns and handling of Ethics & Securities (see ANNEX A1); it also described its data management practices and the guidance it would follow to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of its data (see ANNEX A2). The specific implementation of guidance and principles in the INSIGHT Project is documented in the INSIGHT Data Management Plan (DMP) (INSIGHT Deliverable D3.1)³. The team members will conduct all studies in INSIGHT in adherence to the fundamental ethical principles applicable when conducting the studies.

The INSIGHT consortium has partners from the non-EU countries Switzerland, UK, USA, South Korea, Brazil and Australia. All ethics & security also apply completely to these partners and compliance with the ethical rules and standards, guidelines and directives is ensured by bilateral agreements or equivalent national regulations.

I.1.1 Humans

As described in the ethics assessment of INSIGHT, the Project does not include activities that may influence humans, apart from those involving participants of non-medical studies (e.g. social or human sciences research), which may involve volunteers in relation to stakeholder engagement activities. INSIGHT aims to improve humans' safety, sustainability and socio-economic aspects through the advancement of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework applicability. The Project will seek to establish close contact and collaboration with regulatory and decision-making bodies, as set out in work packages (WPs) 5-6. The consortium has participants across the EU and globally. The cultural interactions are highly cherished and taken into consideration in all dissemination and communication practices. Through special synergies, expected to be established with projects funded under similar Horizon Europe call topics, INSIGHT aims to reach a larger group of stakeholders that will be informed of project results in a popular manner leading to more awareness of the Project research and results amongst citizens across Europe.

I.1.2 Human cells/tissues and animals

INSIGHT research does not involve human cells/cell lines, embryonic or foetal cells or tissues. No animals will be used in INSIGHT.

I.1.3 Harm to the environment and health

INSIGHT does not include activities with potential harm to the environment, or the health of animals or humans. If safety considerations arise during the Project implementation, they will be monitored and carefully handled. All the precautions to ensure safety of the research staff and of the environment will be taken by the institutions responsible for the handling and final disposal of the relevant chemicals.

³ INSIGHT Deliverable Report 3.1 'Data Management Plan (DMP)', delivery at M3, final update at M48.

1.1.4 Personal data

Personal data need to be collected for administrative reasons (e.g. biographic metadata associated with the data, registrations to events and online services). These only include the minimal information required and do not have any information on ethnic, social or sex/gender aspects. Personal data are processed in the Project without involving the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g. genetic data) and without profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals, or processing of large scale of special categories of data or intrusive methods of data processing or by using previously collected datasets. Specific provisions on treatment of personal data, in relation to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), are described in detail in section 3.2.

1.1.5 Non-EU countries

The Project requires no sharing of personal data with third parties inside or outside the EU. Sharing of data between EU, Swiss or UK partners and associated countries (USA, South Korea, Brazil and Australia) is reduced to the absolute minimum and organised fully compliant with all relevant EU Directives. Personal data exports from/to non-EU countries may occur as part of stakeholder registration/communication, and/or event Organisation (e.g. registrants' name, email-address). In case personal data are transferred from the EU to a non-EU country or international organisation, confirmation that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679, is submitted as a deliverable. No material exchange or imports/exports to non-EU countries is foreseen in INSIGHT.

1.1.6 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) will be used in INSIGHT for data analysis, text mining and potentially for development of machine-learning to support the development of QSAR and other models. All these applications fall under the 'low or minimal risk' category of the proposed Artificial Intelligence Act of the European Commission⁴ and are free of any additional legal obligations. Nevertheless, all INSIGHT AI activities will strictly follow the guidance on AI included in the new version of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁵, published in June 2023 and any eventual updates, when they become available.

The INSIGHT Project is committed to upholding the principles of trustworthy AI to ensure the technical robustness of the proposed framework for the integrative impact assessment of chemicals and materials. Such practice ensures that the models integrated into the INSIGHT framework will be FAIR, reliable, transparent, and have clearly defined inputs and outputs. Moreover, INSIGHT will ensure model robustness by employing state-of-the-art consensus learning approaches and model stacking. INSIGHT will also focus on enhancing the accessibility and transparency of existing models, making them FAIR and easily understandable by a wider audience. Ultimately, INSIGHT aims to democratise AI-based models and complex data, through the provision of comprehensive manuals, guidelines, and examples based on the case studies.

The use of general-purpose AI and generative AI models such as large language models (e.g. ChatGPT) is currently not foreseen in INSIGHT. If this changes in the future, INSIGHT will apply the mandatory requirements for the General purpose and generative AI of the Artificial Intelligence Act.

⁴ EU AI Act: first regulation on artificial intelligence: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20230601STO93804/eu-ai-act-first-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence> (website accessed: 21.02.2024).

⁵ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity: <https://allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/European-Code-of-Conduct-Revised-Edition-2023.pdf> (website accessed: 21.02.2024)

2 Ethics management in INSIGHT

Ethics management is a horizontal topic that will be monitored for all the activities during the duration of the INSIGHT Project. Ethical compliance will be monitored, in particular, through T7.4 Project-internal Guidance on Gender Dimensions and Ethics which is led by the Project Coordinator (PC), TAU, and supported by all Project Partners. The aim of all ethics activities, including the Ethical Guideline, in the Project is to ensure that the provisions on ethics regulations and rules are respected.

The central ethics monitoring tools and activities of INSIGHT are as follows:

- **Ethical guideline:** The document at hand serves as the main tool for all members of the consortium to 1) familiarise themselves with the ethical principles and regulations that the consortium is committed to as well as the ethics issues that need particular attention in the Project, and 2) refer to jointly agreed ethics monitoring activities and guidelines.
- **Shared and personal responsibility:** While TAU leads the Gender Dimensions and Ethics management task (T7.4), each INSIGHT consortium member is responsible for complying with the set of ethical principles and relevant legislation, as described in this guideline. Moreover, all Partners are expected to report on any new ethical issues they might come across during the course of the Project.
- **Regular meetings:** Ethics will be a fixed topic in each General Assembly meeting of the Project. Moreover, ethical issues are going to be discussed in the more frequent Executive Board meetings whenever necessary.
- **Project Quality Management & Risk Management Plan:** The deliverable (D7.2) will be developed, in order to ensure (i) the management of Project-related documentation, (ii) monitoring and quality control of Project deliverables and milestones, and (iii) risk contingency management. Acting according to the agreed principles is crucial for ensuring that the INSIGHT Project is executed in a high-quality, timely, and ethical way.
- **Data Management:** Data management is closely connected to the ethical conduct of research and therefore the Data Management Plan (DMP – D3.1) acts as an important tool for ensuring good ethics practices as well. The DMP will be updated regularly throughout the Project.
- **Process for handling allegations of research misconduct:** As described in Section 4 below in this document, the INSIGHT consortium has a zero-tolerance policy for research misconduct, disregard for responsible conduct of research and other unacceptable practices in research. Should any consortium member detect such activity, they must inform the PC without delays. The PC will then investigate the issue and may take necessary actions to ensure that any potential risks, breaches of information, or harm are eliminated or minimised. If necessary, the PC will inform the Project Officer.
- **Record keeping:** the consortium maintains detailed records of all ethical decisions and actions taken during the Project, including minutes of consortium body meetings, reports on any ethical breaches, and documentation of any modifications made to the ethics plan.

Overall, the monitoring and oversight of ethics is an ongoing and dynamic process that should be tailored to the specific ethical issues and risks associated with the research Project. It is essential to maintain open communication within the consortium and with stakeholders and to respond promptly to any ethical concerns that may arise.

3 Guiding Principles, General Obligations and Codes of Conduct pertaining to the INSIGHT Project

3.1 The INSIGHT Grant Agreement

Amongst the Project Beneficiaries (i.e. those Parties, who sign the INSIGHT GA), all matters of Ethics and Research Integrity are governed by Article 14 and Annex 5 INSIGHT GA, while all matters of Data Protection are governed by Article 15 of the INSIGHT GA (ID: 101137742). All Project Parties, who do not sign the GA (i.e. Affiliated Entities and Associated Partners), are bound to the articles of the GA by their signatures of the Consortium Agreement (CA) (cf. Article 4).

Excerpts from Article 14 of the INSIGHT GA:

14.1 Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.

Specific ethics rules (if any) are set out in Annex 5.

14.2 Values

The beneficiaries must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Specific rules on values (if any) are set out in Annex 5.

[...]

Excerpts from Article 15 of the INSIGHT GA:

Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement.

[...]

15.2 Data processing by the beneficiaries

The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/679)⁶.

They must ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects*
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes*
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed*
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date*
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and*
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.*

The beneficiaries may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement. The beneficiaries must ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC ('GDPR') (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679> (website accessed: 21.02.2024).

The beneficiaries must inform the persons whose data are transferred to the granting authority and provide them with the Portal Privacy Statement.

[...]

Excerpts from Annex 5 of the GA, applicable to the INSIGHT Project:

The beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:

- *ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity)*
- *applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols*

[...]

Activities involving research on human embryos or human embryonic stem cells may be carried out only if:

- *they are set out in Annex 1 or*
- *the coordinator has obtained explicit approval (in writing) from the granting authority*

In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity — as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

This implies compliance with the following principles:

- *reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources*
- *honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way*
- *respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment*
- *accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices including ensuring, where possible, openness, reproducibility and traceability and refrain from the research integrity violations described in the Code.*

[...]

Before starting an action task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities.

The documents must be kept on file and be submitted upon request by the coordinator to the granting authority. If they are not in English, they must be submitted together with an English summary, which shows that the documents cover the action tasks in question and includes the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned (if any).

Gender mainstreaming

The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

3.1.1 Ethics & Research Integrity

3.1.1.1 Horizon Europe Rule for Participation - Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Articles 18 and 19)

The legal basis for the ethical principles pertaining to the INSIGHT Project is laid out in Regulation (EU) 2021/695⁷ of the European Parliament and of the Council, with Article 18 and 19 specifying the applicable Ethical Principles (see Box 1 and Box 2).

Box 1: Excerpt from the full text of Regulation Horizon Europe 2021/695

Article 18

Eligible actions and ethical principles

1. Without prejudice to paragraph 2 of this Article, only actions implementing the objectives referred to in Article 3 shall be eligible for funding.

The following fields of research shall not be financed:

- (a) activities aiming at human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- (b) activities intended to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such modifications heritable;
- (c) activities intended to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

2. Research on human stem cells, both adult and embryonic, may be financed depending both on the contents of the scientific proposal and the legal framework of the Member States involved. No funding shall be provided within or outside the Union for research activities that are prohibited in all Member States. No funding shall be provided in a Member State for a research activity which is forbidden in that Member State.

⁷ Establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013 (Text with EEA relevance): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R0695> (website accessed: 21.02.2024).

Article 19

1. Actions carried out under the Programme shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international law, including the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, to the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and to the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection.

2. Legal entities participating in an action shall provide:

an ethics self-assessment identifying and detailing all the foreseeable ethics issues related to the

(a) objective, implementation and likely impact of the activities to be funded, including a confirmation of compliance with paragraph 1 and a description of how it will be ensured;

a confirmation that the activities will comply with the European Code of Conduct for Research

(b) Integrity published by All European Academies and that no activities excluded from funding will be conducted;

(c) for activities carried out outside the Union, a confirmation that the same activities would have been allowed in a Member State; and

for activities making use of human embryonic stem cells, as appropriate, details of licensing and

(d) control measures that shall be taken by the competent authorities of the Member States concerned as well as details of the ethics approvals that shall be obtained before the activities concerned start.

3. Proposals shall be systematically screened to identify actions which raise complex or serious ethics issues and submit them to an ethics assessment. The ethics assessment shall be carried out by the Commission unless it is delegated to the funding body. All actions involving the use of human embryonic stem cells or human embryos shall be subject to an ethics assessment. Ethics screenings and assessments shall be carried out with the support of ethics experts. The Commission and the funding bodies shall ensure the transparency of the ethics procedures without prejudice to the confidentiality of the content of those procedures.

4. Legal entities participating in an action shall obtain all approvals or other mandatory documents from the relevant national, local ethics committees or other bodies, such as data protection authorities, before the start of the relevant activities. Those documents shall be kept on file and provided to the Commission or the relevant funding body upon request.

5. If appropriate, ethics checks shall be carried out by the Commission or the relevant funding body. For serious or complex ethics issues, ethics checks shall be carried out by the Commission unless the Commission delegates this task to the funding body.

Ethics checks shall be carried out with the support of ethics experts.

6. Actions which do not fulfil the ethics requirements referred to in paragraphs 1 to 4 and are therefore not ethically acceptable, shall be rejected or terminated once the ethical unacceptability has been established.

3.1.1.2 The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁸ serves the European research community as a framework for self-regulation across all scientific and scholarly disciplines and for all research settings (Box 3). The European Commission recognises the Code as the reference document for research integrity for all EU-funded research projects and as a model for organisations and researchers across Europe. It contains Principles, guidelines for Good Research Practice, Violations of Research Integrity. The Project Partners will ensure to follow these rules.

Box 3: Excerpt from the full text of The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

The beneficiaries will ensure that the activities under the action do not:

- aim at human cloning for reproductive purposes
- intend to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such modifications heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads, which may be financed)
- intend to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer, or
- lead to the destruction of human embryos (for example, for obtaining stem cells).

This implies compliance with the following principles:

- reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources
- honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way.
- respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment
- accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts

and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices including ensuring, where possible, openness, reproducibility and traceability and refrain from the research integrity violations.

Research activities raising ethical issues must comply with the additional requirements formulated by the ethics panels (including after checks, reviews or audits; see Article 25). Before starting an action task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities. The documents must be kept on file and be submitted upon request by the PC to the granting authority. If they are not in English, they must be submitted together with an English summary, which shows that the documents cover the action tasks in question, and includes the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned (if any).

⁸ European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (revised edition 2023): https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-research-integrity_horizon_en.pdf (website accessed: 18.03.2024)

The recent update of the Code of Conduct added a specific section on AI (Box 4), navigating EU data protection laws (Box 5) and how to approach changes to research impact assessments. The first two are highly relevant for the INSIGHT Project.

Box 4: Guidance on AI from The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

2.3 Research Procedures

- Researchers report their results and methods, including the use of external services or AI and automated tools, in a way that is compatible with the accepted norms of the discipline and facilitates verification or replication, where applicable.

2.8 Reviewing and Assessment

- submissions for publication, funding, appointment, promotion, or reward in a transparent and justifiable manner, and disclose the use of AI and automated tools.

3.1 Research Misconduct and other Unacceptable Practices

Research misconduct is traditionally defined as fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism (the so-called FFP categorisation) in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results:

- ...
- Hiding the use of AI or automated tools in the creation of content or drafting of publications.
- [...]

Box 5: Section on the General Data Protection from The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

2.5 Data Practices and Management

- Researchers inform research participants about how their data will be used, reused, accessed, stored, and deleted, in compliance with GDPR.

3.2 Data Protection - Regulation (EU) 2016/679

Regulation (EU) 2016/679⁹ is responsible for all privacy regulatory obligations and contractual obligations related to ethical issues deriving from the usage of data in the Project. Issues like data protection and anonymity will be under thorough consideration (Box 6 and Box 7).

Personal data - as part of the scientific data - will only be collected in the form of information on the data generator (names, institution, addresses including email required according to the FAIR principle RI.2,¹⁰ see ANNEX A2) and we will take particular care of applying state-of-the-art security measures and treating such sensitive information according to GDPR regulations as outlined in the Ethics section in Part A in the Grant Agreement.

⁹ REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679> (website accessed: 22.02.2024).

¹⁰ The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship Nature (2016) DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18; <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618> (website accessed: 22.02.2024).

Box 6: Key Points" Individuals' Rights" from the Regulation (EU) 2016/679

Individuals' rights

The GDPR strengthens existing rights, provides for new rights and gives individuals more control over their personal data. It includes the following bullet points:

- Easier access to an individual's own data. This includes providing more information on how that data is processed and ensuring that that information is available in a clear and understandable way.
- A new right to data portability. This makes it easier to transmit personal data between service providers.
- A clearer right to erasure (right to be forgotten). When an individual no longer wants their data to be processed and there is no legitimate reason to keep it, the data will be deleted.
- The right to know when their personal data has been breached. Companies and organisations have to notify the relevant data protection supervisory authority and, in cases of serious data breaches, also the individuals affected.

Rules for businesses

The GDPR creates a level playing field for all companies operating in the EU internal market, adopts a technology-neutral approach and stimulates innovation through a number of steps, which include the following:

- A single set of EU-wide rules. A single EU-wide law for data protection increases legal certainty and reduces administrative burden.
- A data protection officer. A person responsible for data protection has to be designated by public authorities and by businesses that process data on a large scale, or whose core activity is the processing of special categories of data, such as health-related data.
- One-stop shop. Businesses only have to deal with one single supervisory authority (in the EU Member State in which they have their main establishment); the relevant supervisory authorities cooperate in the framework of the European Data Protection Board for cross-border cases.
- EU rules for non-EU companies. Companies based outside the EU must apply the same rules when offering services or goods to, or when monitoring the behaviours of, individuals within the EU.
- Innovation-friendly rules. A guarantee that data protection safeguards are built into products and services from the earliest stage of development (data protection by design and by default).
- Privacy-friendly techniques. Pseudonymisation (when identifying fields within a data record are replaced by one or more artificial identifiers) and encryption (when data is coded in such a way that only authorised parties can read it), for example, are encouraged, in order to limit the intrusiveness of processing.
- Removal of notifications. The GDPR scrapped most notification obligations and the costs associated with these. One of its aims is to remove obstacles that affect the free flow of personal data within the EU. This will make it easier for businesses to expand in the single digital market.
- Data protection impact assessments. Organisations will have to carry out impact assessments when data processing may result in a high risk for the rights and freedoms of individuals.
- Record keeping. Small and medium-sized enterprises are not required to keep records of processing activities – unless the processing is regular or likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of the person whose data is being processed, or includes sensitive categories of data.
- A modern toolbox for international data transfers. The GDPR offers various instruments to transfer data outside the EU, including adequacy decisions adopted by the European Commission where the non-EU country offers an adequate level of protection, pre-approved (standard) contractual clauses, binding corporate rules, codes of conduct and certification.

4 Conclusion

At this stage, this document serves as a basic guideline for internal ethical practices within INSIGHT for the beneficiaries and will be continually evolving under the Executive Board of the Project. Work Package (WP) leaders are actively integrating these guidelines into their work, while aligning with European guidelines and laws.

The initial ethics and security criteria were established at the proposal stage, detailed in section 4 of the submitted INSIGHT proposal, and included the completion of the administrative form for ethics & security (ANNEX A1). The first three months of the Project (M03) involved a critical review and refinement of these measures, leading to the V1.0 of this document.

ANNEX A1 – Excerpt from Project Proposal, Section 4 Ethics & Security, p. 155-158

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4 - Ethics & security

Ethics Issues Table

1. Human Embryonic Stem Cells and Human Embryos		Page
Does this activity involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs)?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve the use of human embryos?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
2. Humans		Page
Does this activity involve human participants?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve interventions (physical also including imaging technology, behavioural treatments, etc.) on the study participants?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation (EU 536/2014)? (using pharmaceuticals, biologicals, radiopharmaceuticals, or advanced therapy medicinal products)	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
3. Human Cells / Tissues (not covered by section 1)		Page
Does this activity involve the use of human cells or tissues?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
4. Personal Data		Page
Does this activity involve processing of personal data?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Is it planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Is it planned to import personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve the processing of personal data related to criminal convictions or offences?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
5. Animals		Page
Does this activity involve animals?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
6. Non-EU Countries		Page
Will some of the activities be carried out in non-EU countries?	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	39
UK, Switzerland, USA, South Korea, Australia		
In case non-EU countries are involved, do the activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Is it planned to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Is it planned to import any material (other than data) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? For data imports, see section 4.	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	

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Is it planned to export any material (other than data) from the EU to non-EU countries? For data exports, see section 4.	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve low and/or lower middle income countries , (if yes, detail the benefit-sharing actions planned in the self-assessment)	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the activity at risk?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
7. Environment, Health and Safety		Page
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants.(during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact) ?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity deal with endangered fauna and/or flora / protected areas?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to humans, including those performing the activity.(during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact) ?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
8. Artificial Intelligence		Page
Does this activity involve the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence? (if yes, detail in the self-assessment whether that could raise ethical concerns related to human rights and values and detail how this will be addressed).	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	12
9. Other Ethics Issues		Page
Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> No	
I confirm that I have taken into account all ethics issues above and that, if any ethics issues apply, I will complete the ethics self-assessment as described in the guidelines How to Complete your Ethics Self-Assessment		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

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Ethics Self-Assessment

Ethical dimension of the objectives, methodology and likely impact

The INSIGHT project is committed to upholding the principles of trustworthy AI to ensure the technical robustness of the proposed framework for the integrative impact assessment of chemicals and materials. Such practice ensures that the models integrated into the INSIGHT framework will be FAIR, reliable, transparent, and have clearly defined inputs and outputs. Moreover, INSIGHT will ensure model robustness by employing state-of-the-art consensus learning approaches and model stacking. INSIGHT will also focus on enhancing the accessibility and transparency of existing models, making them FAIR and easily understandable by a wider audience. Ultimately, INSIGHT aims to democratise AI-based models and complex data, through the provision of comprehensive manuals, guidelines, and examples based on the case studies.

Remaining characters 4180

Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations

Describe how the issue(s) identified in the ethics issues table above will be addressed in order to adhere to the ethical principles and what will be done to ensure that the activities are compliant with the EU/national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks are to be carried out. It is reminded that for activities performed in a non-EU countries, they should also be allowed in at least one EU Member State.

Remaining characters 5000

ANNEX A2 – Excerpt from “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” (Wilkinson et al., 2016)

The FAIR Guiding Principles

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

